

1 CD142: Johanngeorgenstadt–Karlovy Vary

CD142 is a short line that would look like an obvious choice for BEMUs, if it were not that it passes through Pernink, the second highest rail station in Czechia, with an increase of almost 500 metres from the lower terminus at Karlovy Vary; from Pernink, the line continues down to the German border, ending less than 1 km after passing it in the town of Johanngeorgenstadt. Only a very short section of few km is electrified around Karlovy Vary.

Figure 2: The altitude profile of line CD142.

The line has a traffic of 364 754 train-km a year, and employs 5 MUs; the current vehicles are a mix of old 810 single-wagon units and newer 2-wagon RegioShark, which were preferred in the simulations due to closer similarity with the alternatives Mireo+B and iLint.

The SoC diagrams for battery and hydrogen trains are shown in figure 3: it is evident that a BEMU is able to climb from Karlovy Vary up to Pernink, but will arrive in Johannengeorgenstadt with only about 70 kWh of energy, insufficient to climb back to Pernink, which requires 125 kWh. For this reason, a charger will be required in Johanngeorgenstadt, which due to the absence of any rail electrification and the small population of the area (leading to a presumably weak grid) will be an expensive deployment (10 M€). On the Karlovy Vary side, the short AC electrification is sufficient to recharge BEMUs to 100 %, making it unnecessary to have an additional charging station there, even in case of immediate turnaround.

DC BEMU units could not use this OLE infrastructure in Czechia, and therefore would need an additional charging station in Karlovy Vary; however, as the station is already electrified, a simpler charger (2 M€) would be sufficient.

The slope towards Pernink is actually so steep that, both ways on the way down, hydrogen trains do not need to use fuel cells, and may operate only on their buffer battery; this has not been modelled in the techno-economic analysis, but may halve the operating time of fuel cells—and thereby double their lifetime.

The techno-economic analysis, shown in figure 4, indicates that the most advantageous alternative for CD142 is actually HMU: this is primarily due to the requirement of a charging station in Johanngeorgenstadt driving up costs for BEMUs. In any case, all hydrogen, battery and diesel trains have similar economy, with the sequence slightly altered in the lumped approach.

Figure 3: State of charge of batteries on BEMUs and H(E)MUs on CD142.

Figure 4: Equivalent annual costs of operating various technologies on CD142; marginal approach on the left, lumped on the right.

2 L7: Liberec–Seifhennersdorf

L7 is another short line, with the particularity of having no electrified section whatsoever, and no access to electrical power at either terminus. L7 crosses multiple borders: from Seifhennersdorf, it first enters Czechia at Varnsdorf, then returns into Germany at Großschönau, leaves Germany after Zittau for Poland, where no stops are made, and re-enters Czechia at Hrádek nad Nisou. The elevation profile of line L7 is fairly flat, with its bottom at Zittau.

Figure 5: The altitude profile of line L7.

The line has a traffic of 611 010 train-km a year, and employs 6 MUs; the current vehicles are a mix of Desiro, RegioSpider and RegioSprinter; Desiros were preferred in the simulations due to closer similarity with the alternatives Mireo+B and iLint.

The SoC diagrams for battery and hydrogen trains are shown in figure 6: the round trip requires about exactly the full charge available on a BEMU, indicating that a BEMU may service the line with a single charging station, likely to be deployed in Liberec, assuming sufficiently fast turnaround times in Seifhennersdorf. As Liberec is not electrified, the charging station will be of the expensive sort, 10 M€. Since no infrastructure is present on this line, it does not matter for this analysis whether the BEMUs will be AC or DC.

Figure 6: State of charge of batteries on BEMUs and H(E)MUs on L7.

The techno-economic analysis, shown in figure 7, indicates that the most advantageous alternative for L7 is DMU: an important contribution is the lower access fees due to the lighter frame of the Desiro trains.

BEMUs are slightly ahead of HMUs, but if after successive evaluations it were to be found that a charger is needed in Seifhennersdorf, the evaluation would turn clearly in favour of HMUs. As no OLE is available, HEMUs were not considered.

Figure 7: Equivalent annual costs of operating various technologies on L7; marginal approach on the left, lumped on the right.

3 RB1: Zwickau-Karlovy Vary

RB1 is a longer line with significant stretches in both Czechia and Germany, AC-electrified at both termini and with a significant OLE section (over 20 km) between Sokolov and Karlovy Vary. Note that the Czech and German AC do not only have different voltage (resp. 25 kv and 15 kV), but also frequency (50 Hz vs. 16.7 Hz): BEMUs able to use both systems may or may not be available.

The elevation profile features a significant rise up to Schöneck, at over 750 m, roughly placed symmetrically in the middle of the line.

Figure 8: The altitude profile of line RB1.

The line has a traffic of 859 032 train-km a year, and employs 8 MUs; the current vehicles are a mix of RegioSpider and RegioSprinter; RegioSpiders were selected for the simulations.

The SoC diagrams for battery and hydrogen trains are shown in figure 9: each way, BEMUs can complete the line within their SoC constraints only if they can exploit the Czech OLE infrastructure. Zwickau Hbf is also AC-electrified, but according to the German standard: if a BEMU is only able to accept the Czech one, an additional charging station will be required, of the cheaper sort (2 M€) since electrification is already available in Zwickau, and there is only the matter of converting voltage and frequency.

Figure 9: State of charge of batteries on BEMUs and H(E)MUs on RB1.

The techno-economic analysis, shown in figure 10, indicates that the most advantageous alternative for RB1 is DMU: this is however mostly due to the lower weight of RegioSpiders compared to 2-wagon MUs (both Mireo+B and iLint).

BEMUs are however only barely behind DMUs, and the necessity of a charger in Zwickau has minimal impact on the decision since it is of the cheaper sort: H(E)MUs are measurably behind in this case, due to larger energy costs.

Figure 10: Equivalent annual costs of operating various technologies on RB1; marginal approach on the left, lumped on the right.

4 RB2: Zwickau-Plauen-Cheb

RB2 and RB5 were initially requested to be analysed together, but given the results of this section they will be presented separately.

RB2 is a line of length similar to RB1, also originating in Zwickau and running somewhat parallel to RB1, but ending in Cheb. It features significant stretches of AC-electrification at both Czech and German ends, of course in their respective voltages and frequencies. The non-electrified section is just about 60 km between Plauen and Vojtanov.

The elevation profile rises overall about 200 m from Zwickau to Cheb, with a top in Bad Brambach (600 m) at the border.

Figure 11: The altitude profile of line RB2.

The line is assumed to carry 40% of the combined RB2-RB5 traffic of 1 690 680 train-km a year, and 40% of their combined 12 MUs (i.e. 4.8, which is not a whole number, but will be kept for consistency; results are unaffected); the current vehicles are Siemens Desiro.

The SoC diagrams for battery and hydrogen trains are shown in figure 12: the diagram is now made more complicated by the several possible variants of BEMU: the one that can exploit both OLE systems (“BEMU”), the one that can exploit neither (“BEMU (DC)”), and the ones that can use only one (“BEMU (DE)” and “BEMU (CZ)”); a similar distinction is shown for HEMUs (without any “HEMU (DC)” that would be the same as HMU).

It is evident from figure 12 that only BEMUs able to exploit the German AC OLE can successfully reach Cheb on the net uphill southward route. BEMUs that cannot exploit the Czech OLE will arrive with only 100 kWh, which is far below the 200 kWh necessary to reach again Plauen from Cheb: these will require a charging station in Cheb, again of the cheaper sort (2 M€) since Cheb station is already electrified.

It can be noticed that HEMUs able to use both OLE systems would barely make use of fuel cells at all, especially in the northwards direction.

The techno-economic analysis, shown in figure 13, indicates a clear preference for BEMUs: even if these cannot use the Czech OLE and require a charging station in Cheb, their result is clearly superior to alternatives.

Curiously, this line is one of the few cases where HEMUs perform better than HMUs, since they have significantly cheaper energy costs as there is so much of the line equipped with OLE.

Figure 12: State of charge of batteries on BEMUs and H(E)MUs on RB2.

Figure 13: Equivalent annual costs of operating various technologies on RB2; marginal approach on the left, lumped on the right.

5 RB5: Mehltheuer–Plauen–Kraslice

RB2 and RB5 were initially requested to be analysed together, but given the results of this section they will be presented separately.

RB5 is a somewhat shorter line sharing some track with both RB1 and RB2, originating in Mehltheuer (close to Plauen) and proceeding south until Kraslice. From Mehltheuer until Herlasgrün, the line is AC-electrified (with German standard); the other terminus, Kraslice, is not electrified.

The two termini have a similar elevation (500 m), and the highest point in the line is Schöneck, at over 750 m, closer to the Czech terminus.

Figure 14: The altitude profile of line RB5.

The line is assumed to carry 60% of the combined RB2-RB5 traffic of 1 690 680 train-km a year, and 60% of their combined 12 MUs (i.e. 4.8, which is not a whole number, but will be kept for consistency; results are unaffected); the current vehicles are Siemens Desiro.

The SoC diagrams for battery and hydrogen trains are shown in figure 15: the line can be covered by any fully-charged BEMU. BEMUs able to exploit the German OLE will arrive in Kraslice with higher SoC (130 kWh), but it will not be sufficient to return to Herlasgrün (160 kWh) are required: a charger in Kraslice, of the expensive sort (10 M€), will be required, as Kraslice is not an electrified station.

Figure 15: State of charge of batteries on BEMUs and H(E)MUs on RB5.

The techno-economic analysis, shown in figure 16, shows that BEMUs (able to use German AC OLE) are the preferred solution, even if there is a significant component of cost for the Kraslice charger: the result is

different from that of CD142, which had a similar cost structure, because the cost is spread on more MUs which run more kilometres a year: i.e., the charger is simply more in use.

Figure 16: Equivalent annual costs of operating various technologies on RB5; marginal approach on the left, lumped on the right.

6 U8-T2: Děčín-Rumburk-Mikulášovice

U8 and T2 are two lines considered as one in this study; while the line is close to the German border, especially at the Mikulášovice terminus, it is completely in Czechia. The timetables of U8 and T2 are significantly different, with far less traffic currently present on T2; for this analysis, we assumed that according to the current timetable a train would have a long stopover in Rumburk before continuing either way.

The line is almost completely non-electrified, except a very brief DC section between Děčín and Děčín východ. The elevation profile sees a significant rise from Děčín (100 m) up to Jedlová (over 500 m), after which elevation remains approximately constant.

Figure 17: The altitude profile of line U8T2.

The line has a combined traffic of 431 848 train-km a year (of which only 28 722 on T2, but this datum will not be used), and employs 5 MUs. The current MUs are a mix of RegioShark (U8) and series 810 (T2); for the simulations, RegioShark will be used as DMU.

The SoC diagrams for battery and hydrogen trains are shown in figure 18: the downhill, southward direction can be traversed with a BEMU, even considering the large SoC drop in Rumburk due to the long waiting time (90 minutes); however, the uphill leg requires too much energy, even if the stop in Rumburk could be shortened.

For this reason, a charger in Rumburk is mandatory; this will again be of the more expensive sort (10 M€) as there is no electrification available there. Note that without the stop in Rumburk, the BEMU option would have simply been infeasible.

Figure 18: State of charge of batteries on BEMUs and H(E)MUs on U8T2.

The techno-economic analysis, shown in figure 19, shows that BEMUs and HMUs are essentially even, with the costs of the Rumburk charger for BEMUs almost exactly compensating the higher fuel costs of HMUs.

Figure 19: Equivalent annual costs of operating various technologies on U8T2; marginal approach on the left, lumped on the right.

7 Concluding Remarks

The analysis of these lines has highlighted how several of these are appropriate for BEMU usage; only CD142 seems to produce a preference for HMUs. As expected, BEMU performance improves for lines with pre-existing OLE, and where chargers can be set up piggybacking on pre-existing grid infrastructure, e.g. with AC/AC transformers. In several lines, however, HMU performance is quite close to BEMU, e.g. U8T2 and L7. The RB lines, instead, show a more marked preference for BEMU.

It should be remarked that the price of hydrogen is a significant factor in HMU operation cost, and has been calculated to a very high value (8.5 €/kg) by calculating conservatively that the **same electricity price** will apply to BEMU charging stations and electrolyzers. This is expected to be somewhat untrue because:

- BEMUs will charge during the day, when energy prices are higher;
- Hydrogen can be produced by electrolysis selectively when energy prices are lower;
- Most of BEMU charging will be non-dispatchable and require significant power ratings (possibly in the MW range), which will imply significant power tariffs (not modelled in this study);
- Hydrogen production is dispatchable and may instead make use of cheap, disconnectible tariffs;
- Electrolysers may also tap into a parallel revenue stream by selling balancing services to the grid;
- Hydrogen sources from e.g. industrial by-product may be cheaper than production from electrolysis.

The data necessary to calculate these effects was not available nor within the scope of RegioHyt, but should be carefully evaluated before an investment decision is made.

Another hypothesis that was not considered is the **effect of degradation on batteries**: the admissible SoC window in simulations goes from 20 % to 80 % of the nominal capacity, which means that at end of life (when the nominal capacity is 80 % of the nominal), the battery will actually be cycling between 10 % and 70 % of the nominal capacity; this may accelerate degradation, and if it were to be assumed that batteries could then only be cycled between 20 %–80 % of the *current* capacity, the dimensioning limit would be from 16 % to 64 %, i.e. 48 % of nominal capacity instead of the 60 % we used: this may trigger the need for further chargers or make some routes impassable.

Finally, several of these routes were not planned with recharging times in mind, and **turnaround times** may be insufficient for BEMU recharge:

- 15 minutes in Karlovy Vary for CD142;
- 5–10 minutes in Liberec for L7;
- 3–5 minutes total stop in Zwickau Hbf for RB1, whose terminus is actually Zwickau Zentrum and where it stops only 7 minutes; Zwickau Z. is indeed electrified, but as a tramway (600 V), not a railway, and is unlikely to have sufficient power capacity;
- RB2 does *not* have the same problem, since after passing Zwickau Hbf it remains under AC OLE for over 40 km until Plauen, and BEMUs would have plenty of time to recharge;
- 10 minutes at the Cheb terminus of RB2 for BEMUs compatible only with German AC, likely sufficient as only a minor top-up is required;
- 20 minutes in Kraslice for RB5, likely sufficient as only a minor top-up is required;
- 15 minutes in Děčín for U8 should be sufficient, in combination with the short DC OLE section from Děčín východ.